

Title: Is neural entrainment to rhythms the basis of social bonding through music?

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Abstract:

Music utilizes the evolutionarily unique temporal sensitivity of the auditory system and its tight coupling to the motor system to create a common neurophysiological clock between individuals that facilitates action coordination. We propose that this shared common clock arises from entrainment to musical rhythms, the process by which partners' brains and bodies become temporally aligned to the same rhythmic pulse.

Main body:

Many human biological processes - from breathing to walking - are rhythmic. Savage et al. propose entrainment as one neurobiological underpinning of music's social effects. *Here we clarify the concept of entrainment and its neurobiological mechanisms, arguing that entrainment should take the central role in the discussion of music's social origins.*

Entrainment is the process by which two – or more - oscillatory (fluctuating) processes become coupled via phase or frequency adjustment (Pikovsky, 2003). When two oscillators are entrained, they are temporally aligned, such as when musicians synchronize to another’s tone onsets (Demos et al., 2019). This synchronization is sustained beyond direct physical coupling, which differentiates entrainment from *resonance*, a term that is often (and incorrectly) used interchangeably with entrainment (Helfrich et al., 2019). In fact, the intention and attention required to maintain behavioral entrainment (Leow et al., 2018) may create the ‘social’ nature of the signal: entrainment in musical group contexts is not simply reflexive or the result of unintentional mirroring.

When an individual entrains their actions with an external oscillation – such as the music of a partner – they achieve *behavioural* synchrony. Growing evidence suggests that behavioural entrainment is governed by *neural entrainment*, the alignment of rhythmic brain activity to external rhythmic stimuli (for a review, see Lakatos, 2019). For music, neural entrainment may alter auditory perception by guiding attention towards rhythmically salient acoustic events (Jones et al., 2002; Henry & Hermann, 2014). Moreover, neural entrainment to perceived rhythms facilitates detection of auditory stimulus features (Henry & Obleser, 2012; Bauer et al., 2018), suggesting that entrainment facilitates more than simply moving along to music.

Merely hearing an auditory rhythm activates motor brain areas (Grahn & Rowe, 2009; Grahn & Brett, 2007; Zatorre et al., 2007), particularly when the rhythm features a salient *beat* (Grahn & Rowe, 2013); a regular, psychologically salient, recurring event in the rhythm. The beat is central to entrainment, as the beat is what people generally synchronize to, and it enables synchronization even to novel music. Perhaps unsurprisingly then, entrainment of neural oscillations to the beat occurs not only in auditory but also in motor regions (Morillon & Baillet, 2017; Fujioka et al., 2009, 2015). Auditory-motor entrainment may be the neural driver behind moving to music; entrainment of beat-related auditory-motor activity influences behavioral synchronization (Nozaradan et al., 2015; Mathias et al., 2020). *We propose that this tight auditory-motor coupling, translating musical rhythms into action, is critical for group music-making.*

Musical partners mutually synchronize auditory and motor brain activity to the sounds that they produce (Mueller et al. 2013, Sanger et al., 2012, 2013; Zamm et al., 2018). In fact, when two brains are synchronized through electrical stimulation, spontaneous (Pan, 2020) and intentional (Novembre et al., 2017) bodily movements also become more synchronized. Moreover, physiological activity is coupled during synchronous musical behavior (Mueller & Lindenberger, 2012; Gordon et al., 2020). Thus, *interpersonal synchrony* operates at behavioral, neural, and physiological levels, all of which may support the social effects of synchronous music-making.

Interpersonal synchrony has been suggested to play an evolutionary role in promoting social cohesion (Launay et al., 2016) by facilitating trust (Launay et al., 2013), affiliation (Hove & Risen, 2009), and prosocial behavior (Cirelli et al., 2014). Consistent with this view, interpersonal behavioral, physiological, and neural synchrony occur between mothers and infants (for a review see Wass et al., 2020), between certain animal species’ movements and computer-generated or conspecific rhythms (Patel et al., 2009; Cook et al., 2013; Lameira et al., 2019). *These links*

between entrainment and social cohesion across adults, children, and certain animals, suggest that entrainment may be the musical feature evolutionarily selected to facilitate bonding.

Interestingly, both infants and animals are poorer at synchronization than adult humans, raising the question of whether precise synchronization and well-honed prediction mechanisms are critical for experiencing the social benefits of interpersonal synchrony, the latter being a central argument of Savage et al. Even adults show a wide range of synchronization abilities (Grahn & Schuit, 2012), yet there is little evidence that poor synchronizers – adults or children – do not enjoy dancing or moving to music, nor that they experience less social affiliation afterward. In fact, anecdotally, the social affiliation within an amateur, less synchronized musical group may surpass that of a professional, highly synchronized group. Therefore, bonding can arise in social entrainment contexts regardless of individuals' ability to synchronize accurately. *Thus, the ability to experience the social benefits of entrainment in group music-making is not necessarily dependent on accurate entrainment ability.*

Overall, auditory entrainment to musical rhythms activates the motor system. During music-making, synchronization of actions, brain rhythms, and physiological activity occurs between musical partners. However, many non-musical behaviors involving *entrained* actions, such as walking side-by-side (Nessler & Gilliland, 2011), rowing (Cohen et al., 2010), and dance (Chauvigne et al., 2019), facilitate interpersonal synchrony of behavior and likely also neural and physiological rhythms. *We argue that entrainment – of bodies and minds – is the key evolutionary mechanism underlying the social bonding that arises in music. The highly rhythmic structure of music – which arises from both well-defined temporal and spectral patterns - makes music a superior facilitator of interpersonal synchrony and bonding to other entrained activities; however, this hypothesis remains to be definitively proven.* We hope that work inspired by this special issue will test how group music-making specifically enhances social bonding beyond other forms of interpersonal entrainment.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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